

Investigating the Relationship Between Brand Experience Dimensions and Brand Resonance through two Different Brands Selected from the Cosmetics and Food Sectors

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Abstract

In today's global competitive environment, where the functional benefits of products and services converge, the concept of experience has become increasingly important for brands in creating customer loyalty. In the present study, the effects of sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual dimensions of brand experience on brand resonance, which represents a high level of active loyalty and interaction in the brand-customer relationship, were examined through two brands selected from two different sectors. The research was carried out using the survey method by reaching a total of 465 people who are users of the relevant brands. In the analysis of the collected data, it was aimed to determine the effect of different dimensions of brand experience on brand resonance separately, and to compare the results by repeating the analysis for both brands. The results obtained in the study show that affective, behavioral and intellectual experiences had a significant effect on brand resonance in both selected brands, while sensory experience dimension did not make a statistically significant contribution to explaining brand resonance.

Keywords: Sensory brand experience, affective brand experience, behavioral brand experience, intellectual brand experience, brand resonance

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1. Introduction

In today's hypercompetitive environment, it has become increasingly important for the businesses to ensure and maintain brand loyalty of customers who have many brand alternatives. It seems inevitable for companies to create a flawless and exciting experience that is different from their competitors to attract consumers' attention, who are exposed to thousands of brands every day in various online and offline environments, to persuade them to purchase and to create brand loyalty (Ramaseshan

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& Stein, 2014, p. 3). The main focus of modern management conception is the creation and maintenance of permanent customer value (Kumar & Reinartz, 2016, p. 36). One of the main ideas of experiential marketing is that the value exist not only in the products and services purchased, but also in the hedonic and experiential elements that surround the product and service, and in consumption itself (Schmitt & Zarantonello, 2013). Therefore, providing exceptional experiences beyond selling products and services has become extremely important in creating customer value (Wiedmann, Labenz, Haase, & Hennigs, 2018). Today, many global companies, such as KPMG, Amazon and Google, employ executives in various positions responsible for creating and managing customer experience (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016, p. 69).

Positive customer experiences have a significant potential to create an affective connection between the brand and the customer as they provide a pleasant experience for customers (Gentile, Spiller, & Noci, 2007). Reinforcing this connection allows customers to make repeat purchases, to recommend the brand to others, and to interact intensely with the brand. Keller (1993) explained this intense level between the brand and the customer with the concept of brand resonance. Brand resonance is a concept that represents the highest level of interaction between the brand and the customer, constituting the final step in Keller's (2003) customer-based brand equity pyramid. It indicates an intense and active loyalty relationship beyond brand loyalty. When brands reach this level, they gain a significant competitive advantage by creating customers who are loyal and willing to pay more for the brand, who actively follow the brand, join or create brand-focused communities, and recommend the brand to their environment. However, it is not easy for a brand to reach the resonance level, it must successfully complete a series of successive steps to achieve this level. In this study, the effects of brand experience dimensions on brand resonance were investigated for two different brands selected from the cosmetics and food sectors.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Brand Experience

Experiential marketing, unlike the traditional marketing approach, describes consumption as a holistic experience by considering the rational and irrational trends in consumer behavior together. It sees people as affective beings as well as rational ones (Addis & Holbrook, 2001; B. Schmitt, 1999), and recognizes the importance of affective aspects in decision-making (Hirschman & Holbrook, 1982). People are living individuals with experiential needs (B. Schmitt, 2009). Therefore, the perception of a good price and quality is not enough to convince them these days. Consumers are also looking for brands that will give them unique and unforgettable experiences (Gentile et al., 2007; B. Schmitt, 2009; Wiedmann et al., 2018). In an increasingly competitive environment, the effective way to distinguish the business from competitors in products

and services whose functional benefits are close to each other is to focus on the design and presentation of experiences to increase customer satisfaction and loyalty (Walls, Okumus, Wang, & Kwun, 2011, p. 10). Affections arising during consumption experiences have a powerful effect on consumers (Iglesias, Singh, & Batista-Foguet, 2011). As a matter of fact, researches show that modern consumers purchase not only products or services, but also an experience toward the product or service (Morrison & Crane, 2007). In other words, in modern-day consumer understanding, which is not content with only the functional benefits of a product or service, the search for intangible benefits such as the experience factor is becoming increasingly important in consumers' choices (Ong, Lee, & Ramayah, 2018; Prentice, Wang, & Loureiro, 2019; B. Schmitt, 1999; Walls et al., 2011; Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2010).

Pioneering studies on experiential transformation in consumer decision-making mechanisms is based on the Holbrook and Hirschman's conceptualism (1982: 135) seeking in consumption toward entertainment, affective and sensory stimulation and fantasy, (Dwivedi, Nayeem, & Murshed, 2018, p. 101). It is known that experience play a substantial role in improving brand familiarity, brand satisfaction and brand trust (Ha & Perks, 2005).

Experiences are acquired through some form of exposure as a result of direct observation and/or participation, and can be real, imaginary or virtual. For example, consumers are considered to live an experience when seeking information about a product or service, reviewing, evaluating, and purchasing it, or during or after usage of the product (Braunsberger & Munch, 1998, p. 25; Dwivedi et al., 2018, p. 101; B. Schmitt, 1999, p. 55). Thus, it can be said that brand experience is an inevitable phenomenon that covers the entire process encountered before, during and after consumption (Brakus, Schmitt, & Zarantonello, 2009; Ding & Tseng, 2015). Because all contact points between the customer and the brand are essentially experiences, and experiences can occur at any stage of the consumption life cycle (Nysveen, Pedersen, & Skard, 2013; Ong et al., 2018). From a brand perspective, experiences are inferences that people create in their minds through their direct or indirect interaction with the brand (Carbone & Haeckel, 2005, p. 1; Iglesias, Markovic, & Rialp, 2019, p. 2).

In the marketing literature, the concept of experience has been examined under different perspectives such as consumption experience, product experience, aesthetic experience, service experience, shopping experience and customer experience (Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2010). On the other hand, it is seen that the concept of brand experience has become increasingly important in recent years (Oliveira, Araujo, & Tam, 2020).

Brand experience is derived from the concept of customer experience and presents experience not only from the customer's point of view, but also depending on the brand. It refers to the individual, multidimensional, cognitive and affective experiences of each customer toward the brand (Ong et al., 2018). Brakus et al. (2009:

53) conceptualized the brand experience as “internal and behavioral subjective consumer responses, given against stimuli toward brand such as a brand’s design, identity, packaging, communication and environment.” Accordingly, the brand experience consists of four dimensions: sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual. This definition adds a new role to the concept of brand. Brand, as it is known, is defined as “the name, term, sign, symbol, design or combination of these elements that identifies the products and services of a seller or group of seller and distinguishes them from competitors. However, in addition to descriptive and distinctive roles of brand, role of providing experience is also indicated (B. H. Schmitt, Brakus, & Zarantonello, 2014, p. 729). The sensory experience is the first experience level based on consumers’ sensory perceptions toward smell, sound, sight, taste and touch (Huang, Lee, Kim, & Evans, 2015, p. 5; Yoon & Youn, 2016, p. 4). The affective dimension refers to consumers’ emotions and internal thoughts toward the brand (Shamim & Mohsin Butt, 2013, p. 105). The intellectual dimension is expressed as the ability of the brands to ensure customers think and be curious. The behavioral experience refers to physical experiences and long-term behavior patterns, (Ding & Tseng, 2015, p. 996) and is about motivational properties of a brand (Yoon & Youn, 2016).

From experience perspective, brand management is not just about traditional brand-related activities, but is about managing processes that will support the sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual customer experience at all customer contact points (Iglesias et al., 2011). Deming (2007: 10) defines branding as the process of creating original, unique and affective experiences (Huang et al., 2015, p. 3). When consumers experience a brand in terms of various stimuli such as name, logo, color, packaging, advertisement, they tend to create a certain brand perception. Therefore, brand experience indicates the internal and personal reactions of consumers who interact with the brand in some way (Kruger, 2018; Morgan-Thomas & Veloutsou, 2013). However, brand experiences do not create a motivational and evaluative situation (Das, Agarwal, Malhotra, & Varshneya, 2019, p. 2). For this reason, brand experience is different from phenomena such as brand attitude, brand loyalty, brand personality and brand interest, despite being related to them (Brakus et al., 2009; Das et al., 2019; B. H. Schmitt et al., 2014).

Brand experiences can be positive or negative, as well as can occur spontaneously or be created in planned/deliberate way. While spontaneous experiences are expected to be short-lived, designed experiences are considered to be long-lived (Brakus et al., 2009, p. 53; Zarantonello & Schmitt, 2010, p. 553). In addition, experiences are personal as they emerge from the interaction between the activity that creates the experience and the mental state of the person (Pine & Gilmore, 1998).

2.2. Brand Resonance

Brand resonance, a concept proposed by Keller (1993) to characterize brand relationships, constitutes the final step in Keller's model called the "Customer-Based Brand Pyramid" or "Brand Resonance Pyramid" (Duman, Ozbal, & Duerod, 2018). The model is based on consumers' perceptions, beliefs and attitudes toward the brand, or briefly what the brand means in the minds of consumers (Moura, Ferreira, Oliveira, & Cunha, 2019). In the consumer-brand relationship, it refers to the willingness of consumers to relate to and connect with the brand (Huang et al., 2015). Besides, brand resonance expresses a high-level interaction between the consumer and the brand. It explains how consumers develop strong and deep behavioral, psychological and social ties toward the brand, and their active supporting role for the focal brand (Badrinarayanan, 2016; Rindfleisch, Wong, & Burroughs, 2006). Keller explains that consumers develop a brand resonance by creating a strong psychological attachment toward the brand, beyond the fact that consumers often use that brand's products (Huang et al., 2015, p. 108). Building a strong brand in Keller's (2001) customer-based brand model depends on successful completion of each step, respectively, by following four consecutive hierarchical steps. The first step of the model is to create an accurate brand identity. In this way, it is targeted to generate breadth and depth of brand awareness. The depth of brand awareness refers to how easily customers recognize or remember the brand. A brand that is easily remembered has a deeper brand awareness than a brand that is only recognized when seen. The breadth refers to various situations in relation with purchase and use/consumption when the brand element comes to mind. A highly recognizable brand has both deep and broad brand awareness. Because it is not enough for a brand to be the first brand that comes to mind, or to have a certain share of mind, it is also important that the brand is situated in the right time and place. Brand salience/brand awareness is important as a first step in the formation of brand equity, but is often not sufficient on its own. The second step is to create brand meaning toward brand performance and brand image in the mind of consumer with strong, positive and unique brand connotations. Brand performance is related to the extent to which the functional needs of its customers are met, while brand image has something to do with the external characteristics of the product or service toward meeting their social and psychological needs. In the third step, positive and accessible brand reactions are brought out (customers' judgments and feelings toward the brand) (Keller, 2001, 2013a). Brand judgments indicate consumers' personal opinions and evaluations toward the functional and symbolic aspects of the brand, such as credibility, superiority, and quality. Affective responses represent the emotions and feelings that the brand evokes in customers (Kotler & Keller, 2012; Moura et al., 2019). In the fourth and last step of the model ultimate and highest level of relationship between the brand and customers is on the focus, and it is aimed to establish an intense and active loyalty relationship between the brand and the customer.

Building a strong brand is considered as a series of steps that depend on the successful completion of each step in the model. The successful completion of these four steps establishes six fundamental brand building blocks, in respective order: (1) brand salience, how easily or often the brand comes to mind; (2) brand performance, what extent the brand meets functional needs; (3) brand image, how much the brand responds to psychological and social needs; (4) brand judgments, opinions and evaluations about the brand; (5) brand emotions, affective reactions toward the brand; and (6) brand resonance, the nature of the relationship with the brand (Badrinarayanan, 2016; Keller, 2001).

Brand resonance, which is the most valuable among them, occurs when all other brand building blocks are established. Resonance represents, in addition to the breadth or depth of the psychological attachment that customers create toward the brand, the level of activity (repetitive purchasing behaviors, searching for brand information, etc.) that this loyalty leads to (Badrinarayanan, 2016; Keller, 2013b). Keller (2013) addressed these two dimensions of brand resonance in four categories: behavioral loyalty, attitudinal commitment, sense of community, and active participation. The intensity dimension of brand resonance measures attitudinal commitment and sense of community, while the activity dimension provides information about how often consumers purchase and use the brand, as well as activities that are not directly related to purchase and consumption. In the Brand Resonance Pyramid, the left side of the model represents the rational path in brand formation and the right side represents the affective path (Duman et al., 2018, p. 3; Keller, 2016, p. 4; Moura et al., 2019, p. 9). Strong brands go up on both sides of the pyramid. Although the crossover effects between the right and left sides are accepted in the model, it is regarded that brand performance affects brand judgments and brand image affects brand affections (Keller, 2016). When all building blocks are achieved accurately and respectively, the brand resonance, which is the last step of the pyramid, is reached as a result of the thoughts and judgments of customers toward the brand. Keller's (1993) focus on brand resonance provides a deep feeling toward the brand-customer relationship in a way that customers will be seen as a life partner (Huang et al., 2015, p. 110). A brand's ability to reach the resonance stage depends on the formation of positive cognitive evaluations and affective reactions toward the brand by creating positive connotations with a unique brand identity that is difficult to be imitated by competitors (Moura et al., 2019).

3. Research Model and Hypotheses

In the literature, it is seen that brand experience has been examined in terms of its effects on brand loyalty (Başer, Cintamür, & Arslan, 2016; Brakus et al., 2009; Ding & Tseng, 2015; Iglesias et al., 2011; Nysveen et al., 2013), brand satisfaction (Brakus et al., 2009; Ha & Perks, 2005; Nysveen et al., 2013; Yoon & Youn, 2016), brand awareness (Huang et al., 2015), brand equity (Iglesias et al., 2019; Shamim & Mohsin

Butt, 2013), brand resonance (Huang et al., 2015), and repurchase intention (Ebrahim, Ghoneim, Irani, & Fan, 2016; Ong et al., 2018). In fact, the variables such as brand awareness, brand loyalty, repurchase intention discussed in previous studies reflect different dimensions of brand resonance, as explained in the theoretical part of the study. Therefore, brand resonance proposed by Keller could be considered as an umbrella concept that encompasses all these components. However, it is seen that brand experience was mostly considered as a whole and its effects on the relevant variables were tested. However, as revealed by Nysveen et al. (2013), it is possible for different experience dimensions to have different effects on the related variables. The effect of sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual experience dimensions on variables such as brand loyalty, brand equity, purchase intention or the strength of this effect may also differ depending on the characteristics of the brand examined. Therefore, it is thought that testing the effects of brand experience dimensions on brand resonance separately through the conceptual model (Figure 1) developed in the present study will contribute to the literature. In the light of these information, the following hypotheses were tested.

- H₁: Sensory brand experiences have a positive effect on brand resonance.
H₂: Affective brand experiences have a positive effect on brand resonance.
H₃: Behavioral brand experiences have a positive effect on brand resonance.
H₄: Intellectual brand experiences have a positive effect on brand resonance.

Figure 1. Research Model

4. Research Methodology

In the study, two brands were selected, one from the cosmetics industry (Nivea) and the other from the food industry (Danone) to determine the effect of sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual brand experiences on brand resonance. Thus, it

was aimed to compare the effects of brand experience dimensions on brand resonance in two different product categories. The main reason for selecting these brands is the prevalence of their. In addition, both brands are among the top 100 brands in Forbes' "World's Most Valuable Brands" list. (<https://www.forbes.com/powerful-brands/list/>) (Nivea and Danone ranked 92 and 76 on the list, respectively). In the study, 233 people using the Nivea brand and 232 people using the Danone brand were reached and the data were collected by online survey method. In the first part of the questionnaire, there was a total of 20 statements containing the brand experience dimensions and judgments about the brand resonance, and in the second part, questions for determining the demographic characteristics were included. It is seen that the sample size meets the minimum sample size criterion of Tabachnick and Fidell (2012). $N \geq 50+8m$ (m = the number of independent variables).

The scales whose validity and reliability were tested in previous studies in the literature were used in the study. Brakus et al.'s work (2019) for brand experience dimensions and Huang et al.'s work (2014) for brand resonance were utilized. A 5-point Likert-type scale grading from "1- totally disagree" to "5- totally agree" was used in the questionnaire. Due to the difficulties in collecting data, the convenience sampling method was used in the study, which led to a limitation in the generalization of the research results. Another limitation of the study is the fact that only two brands were selected in the study, and the scale statements were adapted to the relevant brands. In addition, examining brand experience dimensions only in terms of the variables thought to have an effect on brand resonance constitutes another limitation of the study.

4.1. Results and Analysis

4.2. Demographic Results

Table 1 presents the demographic data of the participants. It is seen that most of the participants (62.4%) were female. The majority of the participants was in the age range of 25-44 years. Of those people, 45.6% had an undergraduate degree and 33.4% had a graduate degree. In addition, it is seen that 29.2% of the participants had a monthly income of 5,001 TL or more.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Gender	n	(%)	Educational Level	n	(%)
Female	144	62.1	Primary School	6	2.Haz
Male	88	37.3	High School	23	9.Eyl
Age			Associate degree	20	8.Haz
18-24	37	15.Eyl	Bachelor's degree	116	50.0
25-34	89	38.4	Master's - PhD	67	28.Eyl
25-44	76	32.8	Income		
45-49	15	6.May	1,000 TRY or less	11	4.Tem
50 or above	15	6.May	1,001–2,000 TRY	26	11.Şub
Marital Status			2,001–3,000 TRY	54	23.Mar
Single	134	57.7	3,001–4,000 TRY	42	18.Oca
Married	98	42.2	4,001–5,000 TRY	31	13.Nis
			5,001 TRY or above	68	29.Mar

4.3. Reliability Analysis

The reliability analysis results of the scales used in the study are given in Table 2. According to these results, it is seen that the Cronbach's α coefficients of all scales are above the suggested acceptance limit of 0.70.

Table 2. Reliability Analysis

Variables and Their Dimensions	Number of Question	Cronbach's Alpha
Brand Experience	12	0.883
Sensory Experience	3	0.718
Affective Experience	3	0.731
Behavioral Experience	3	0.713
Intellectual Experience	3	0.723
Brand Resonance	8	0.861

4.4. Analysis Results on the Effect of Brand Experience Dimensions on Brand Resonance

The multiple regression analysis was performed splitting the data set for two brands on the SPSS software to determine the effects of sensory, affective, behavioral and intellectual dimensions of brand experience on brand resonance. The results presented in Table 3 and Table 4 show that established regression models were

significant (Table 3: for Nivea, $F = 61.286$, $p < .00$; Table 4: for Danone, $F = 62.042$, $p < .00$). It is seen that Durbin-Watson values of regression models were in the accepted range of 1-3 (Field, 2009). Thus, it can be said that the independency of error terms was satisfied (Table 3: 1.805 for Nivea; Table 4: 2.081 for Danone) It is seen from the tolerance and VIF values in the same tables that there was no multicollinearity problem in the established regression models. All tolerance values of the variables were greater than the value of $(1-R^2)$ (Hair et al., 2014). The results in Table 3 reveal that the $(1-R^2)$ value in the regression model established for the Nivea brand was 0.482. All tolerance values of the independent variables were greater than 0.482 The results in Table 4 show that the $(1-R^2)$ value in the model established for the Danone brand was 0.478 and the tolerance value for all independent variables was greater than 0.478.

Table 3. Regression Model Coefficients for the Effect of Brand Experience Dimensions on Brand Resonance (Nivea Brand)

Model	Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Significance Level	Co-linearity Statistics	
	B	Standard Error	Beta			Tolerance	VBF
1	Constant	.612	.178		3.443	.001	
	Sensory	.054	.058	.056	.944	.346	.600
	Affective	.299	.056	.350	5.330	.000	.490
	Behavioral	.190	.065	.196	2.934	.004	.473
	Intellectual	.220	.055	.246	3.965	.000	.549
$R = .720$ $R^2 = .518$ Adjusted $R^2 = .510$ $F = 61.286$ $p = .000$ Durbin-Watson = 1.805							

Table 4. Regression Model Coefficients for the Effect of Brand Experience Dimensions on Brand Resonance (Danone Brand)

Model	Non-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Significance Level	Co-linearity Statistics	
	B	Standard Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	Constant	.729	.178		4.212	.000	
	Sensory	-.025	.055	-.027	-.457	.648	.590
	Affective	.247	.059	.274	4.193	.000	.492
	Behavioral	.123	.060	.131	2.056	.041	.520
	Intellectual	.397	.058	.439	6.847	.000	.511
$R = .723$ $R^2 = .522$ Adjusted $R^2 = .514$ $F = 62.042$ $p = .000$ Durbin-Watson = 2.081							

As seen in Table 3 showing the results for the Nivea brand, approximately 51% of the variability in brand resonance was explained by brand experience dimensions (Adjusted $R^2 = .514$). On the other hand, it is seen that the effect of affective ($\beta = .350$; $p < .01$), behavioral ($\beta = .196$; $p < .01$) and intellectual ($\beta = .246$; $p < .01$) experience dimensions was statistically significant on brand resonance, while the effect of sensory experience dimension was not statistically significant ($\beta = .056$; $p > .05$).

Similar results were obtained for the Danone brand as presented in Table 4. It was found that, the effect of affective ($\beta = .274$; $p < .01$), behavioral ($\beta = .131$; $p < .05$) and intellectual ($\beta = .439$; $p < .01$) experience dimensions was statistically significant on brand resonance, while the effect of sensory experience dimension was not statistically significant ($\beta = .027$; $p > .05$). According to these results, H_1 hypothesis was rejected, while H_2 , H_3 and H_4 hypotheses were accepted.

Although both brands have various prominent features appealing the sensory organs of consumers (e.g., smell and touch for the Nivea brand products; taste and smell for the Danone brand products), it is noteworthy to determine that the sensory experience dimension did not have a statistically significant effect on brand resonance in both brands. However, considering the fact that brand resonance represents an advanced level of active loyalty and interaction in the customer-brand relationship, it may be assumed that the sensory experiences of the brands did not trigger such an interaction level in the consumers participating in the study.

It is seen that the most effective dimension on brand resonance was affective experience ($\beta = .350$) for the Nivea brand, while intellectual experience ($\beta = .439$) for the Danone brand. Thus, it can be concluded that experiences that appeal to the emotions of consumers gain importance in the development of an active, loyal, following and supporting customer base by the Nivea brand representing the cosmetics industry, while intellectual experiences such as the connotations and curiosity created in the minds of consumers become prominent in the Danone brand representing the food industry.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In today's intense competitive conditions, it is increasingly important for businesses to create brand equity and to generate a customer base that is actively connected to the brand. The concept of brand resonance refers to a deep and strong psychological attachment of customers toward the brand. Thus, an active loyalty relationship emerges between the brand and the customer (Keller, 2013b; Rindfleisch et al., 2006). In this context, the results of the present study reveals the importance of brand experience dimensions in creating brand resonance. Positive experiences toward the brand have an important potential in developing the relationship between the brand

and consumers (Gentile et al., 2007). In this study, it was aimed to determine the effects of different dimensions of brand experience on brand resonance separately, and the said effects toward the brands selected from two different sectors were examined. It was concluded at the end of the study that affective, behavioral and intellectual experience dimensions had a significant and positive effect on brand resonance, but sensory experience dimension had no statistically significant effect on brand resonance for both brands selected from different sectors. Since brand resonance can be considered as an umbrella phenomenon that encompasses many elements such as loyalty, repurchase intention and joining brand communities, as mentioned in the theoretical part of the study, it can be thought that the sensory experiences of the people participating in the study were not sufficient to resonate with the brand, in other words, to provide the highest level of interaction with the brand. However, this should not suggest that sensory experiences are ineffective or unnecessary. Although sensory elements such as sight, sound, smell and taste do not trigger a high level of loyalty for the selected brands in the study, they can contribute to the brand in many different ways (brand awareness, preference, etc.). Similarly, in the study conducted to investigate toward the effect of brand experience dimensions on customer loyalty, Ong et al. (2018) concluded that while sensory experiences positively affected customers' willingness to pay more for the brand and their intention to repurchase, they did not contribute to recommending the brand to others, which is considered a loyalty behavior, and sharing positive messages for the brand.

Although the results cannot be generalized due to the scope and limitations of the study, it can be said that each dimension of brand experience, which is mostly considered as a whole in the literature, does not contribute equally to the formation of brand resonance toward brands. Thus, according to the results obtained in the study, it is seen that the affective experience dimension for the Nivea brand and the intellectual experience dimension for the Danone brand become prominent in the development of brand resonance.

Although studies about the role of experience in the consumer decision-making process have gained importance since the early 1980s, it is considered that the concept of brand experience is still a phenomenon in the literature that needs to be investigated (Iglesias et al., 2011; Shamim & Mohsin Butt, 2013). Empirical studies in the literature indicate that the scale developed by Brakus et al. (2009) were mainly used to measure brand experience, and the effects of brand experience as a whole on various phenomena were investigated. However, considering the unique conditions and status of each brand and product, it is natural that different dimensions of experience become important in an active loyalty relationship. Also, not every brand may appeal to all relevant experience dimensions (Kruger, 2018). Brand experiences indeed are not equal in terms of strength and intensity. While some experiences can be ordinary and average, some are powerful and memorable (Brakus et al., 2009; Iglesias et al., 2019). Accordingly, it can be stated that the results obtained by testing the effects of individual brand experience dimensions on brand resonance make a novel contribution to the literature.

As explained in the theoretical part of the study, experiences can occur spontaneously or be created deliberately since they refer to inferences in the minds of consumers, based on the direct or indirect interactions of the brand and the consumer, covering the whole process before and after consumption (Iglesias et al., 2019; Nysveen et al., 2013). Therefore, as supported by the results of this study, the experiential interactions that businesses will design in accordance with their brands can be considered to contribute significantly to the creation of a loyal customer base. The formation of brand experience is not dependent on the condition that consumers purchase and use a brand. All contact points between people and the brand (e.g., seeing the brand in a store, watching its commercial on TV, etc.) are each an experience. The fact that businesses provide consumers with different and memorable experiences from competitors by identifying the accurate contact points will contribute to customer-based brand equity.

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